

FUTURE ADMINISTRATIVE SYSTEM USE OF PRIVATE CLOUD-BASED COMPUTING ARCHITECTURE IN DELTA STATE COLLEGE OF EDUCATION, MOSOGAR

BY

IGBUNU, Richard O.¹ & FOLE, Mary²

^{1&2}Delta State College of Education, Mosogar

Department of Computer Science

richard.igbunu@descoem.edu.ng & fole.mary@descoem.edu.ng

mobile contact: 08037843686 & 08131059991

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17633843>

Abstract

The study investigates the potential adoption of a private cloud-based computing architecture as a future administrative framework for Delta State College of Education, Mosogar, Nigeria. A private cloud architecture provides enhanced data security, better administrative control, and flexible system customization. The proposed model incorporates critical features like user authentication, role-based access control, and integration with key platforms such as the Learning Management System (LMS) and Human Resource (HR) systems, designed to support remote access, automated provisioning, and real-time monitoring to enhance administrative efficiency. The research outlines the four main types of cloud computing architectures, which are; private, public, hybrid, and multi-cloud with the explanation of the core service models. For effective implementation, the proposed system utilizes clustered resources such as computing power, storage, and networking to ensure scalability and performance. A general architectural framework and implementation roadmap are presented, highlighting the strategic role of cloud technology in modernizing educational administration. The study concludes by recommending the private cloud approach as a means to improve operational effectiveness, ensure data integrity, and strengthen the institution's administrative capacity.

Keywords: Private, Cloud-based, Administrative System, Computing Architecture, Future.

Introduction

The Delta State College of Education, Mosogar (DESCOEM), has made strides in integrating technology into its administrative processes. Notably, some institution in Delta State utilizes the WAeUP.Kofa Student Management System, which streamlines various student-related administrative tasks and has a connective computing system to make administrative purpose easier. However, like many higher education institutions in Nigeria, DESCOEM faces challenges in fully implementing comprehensive computer-based administrative systems. So, there is the need to look into the future administrative system use of private cloud-based computing architecture in the Delta State College of Education Mosogar.

The invention of computing in the 1960s, which permitted numerous users to access a single computer at once, is where the idea of cloud computing first emerged. Nonetheless, the late 1990s saw the introduction of the contemporary idea of cloud computing, which entails the distribution of computer resources via the internet. Ramnath Chellappa (1997) first used the phrase "cloud computing" in a paper he presented in 1997, to describe the new paradigm of providing computing services online. Islam, et al (2023), stated that cloud computing didn't start to gain traction as a business idea until the middle of the 2000s, when virtualization and web services were developing. Microsoft Azure and Google Cloud Platform (GCP), both of which debuted in 2008, were further early cloud providers. The researchers further stated that since then, cloud computing has spread widely,

and businesses of all sizes can now choose from a variety of cloud services and providers.

Griffith (2015) stated that without requiring direct user management, cloud computing is the on-demand availability of computer system resources, particularly processing power and data storage (cloud storage). Large cloud operations are frequently dispersed over several sites, each of which is a data center. Cloud computing typically uses a "pay as you go" model, which can save upfront expenses but exposes consumers to unanticipated ongoing expenditures. Cloud computing relies on resource sharing for consistency. According to Wikipedia (2022), "the whole provider-managed suite of hardware and software can be thought of as an amorphous cloud; the group of networked elements providing services need not be individually addressed or managed by users."

Red (2022), stated that there are four types of cloud computing and they are:

- Private cloud: The researcher further explained that a private cloud is a type of cloud computing environment that is dedicated to a single organization or business. It is typically used by large enterprises or organizations that require high levels of security, control, and customization over their IT infrastructure. In a private cloud, the computing resources, such as servers, storage, and networking, are virtualized and provided as a service to users within the organization
- Public cloud: He stated that the public clouds are cloud computing environments that are often built using IT infrastructure not owned by the end users.
- Hybrid cloud: Chamkour (2021) stated that a hybrid cloud is an IT environment made up of several environments that appear to be connected by LANs, WANs, VPNs, and/or APIs to form a single, unified environment. Hybrid cloud characteristics are complex, and different requirements may apply

- Multi cloud: Red (2022), explained that multi cloud architecture consists of multiple cloud services from various public or private cloud vendors. Although not all multi clouds are hybrid clouds, all hybrid clouds are multi clouds. When numerous clouds are linked together by integration or orchestration, they become hybrid clouds.

Three main types of cloud computing services are: i. Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS). ii. Platforms-as-a-Service (PaaS). iii. Software-as-a-Service (SaaS).

Roshna (2022) stated that the cloud architecture is divided into two parts and they are:

1. Frontend: The Frontend of the cloud architecture refers to the clients side of cloud computing system. It contains all the user interfaces and application which are used by the client to access the cloud computing services /resources. For example, use of a web to access the cloud platform.
2. Backend: The Backend refers to the cloud itself which is used by the service provider. It contains the resources as well as manages the resources and provides security mechanisms. Along with this, includes huge storage, virtual applications, virtual machines, traffic control mechanisms, deployment models and others.

Literature Review

Cloud computing offers scalable, cost-effective, and flexible IT solutions. According to Hassan et al. (2022), Erdogmus (2009), and Red (2022), it eliminates the need for extensive upfront investment and supports dynamic resource allocation. These features make it particularly appealing for educational institutions looking to expand administrative capabilities without significantly increasing operational costs. Optimizing cloud configuration is crucial for balancing performance and cost. An inefficient configuration can result in unnecessary expenses or compromised service quality. Therefore,

selecting the appropriate service and deployment model is vital. In particular, private cloud architecture provides institutions with enhanced control, security, and compliance (Marinescu, 2013). It allows customization of infrastructure to meet specific organizational needs while retaining the benefits of virtualization. According to Zhang et al. (2010), private clouds are ideal for environments where data sensitivity and regulatory constraints are paramount.

In the educational sector, private cloud solutions support secure access to resources, centralized data management, and integration of academic and administrative services. Buyya et al. (2013) emphasize that designing an efficient private cloud requires careful planning of resource allocation, virtualization layers, and network infrastructure. Mishra and Jaiswal (2012) further highlight the importance of scalability and disaster recovery planning in private cloud environments. Moreover, Vaquero et al. (2009) point out that interoperability and service orchestration are essential design components that impact the success of private cloud implementation. When properly designed, a private cloud architecture enhances institutional agility, improves service delivery, and ensures that mission-critical operations are not compromised.

General steps in setting up a private cloud computing and the Design of Proposed Administrative System Cloud-Based Computing architecture for Delta State College of Education, Mosogar

Setting up a private cloud computing architecture involves several key steps to ensure security, scalability, and efficient resource management. Here's a general roadmap:

1. **Planning & Requirements Analysis:** In this stage objectives are defined e.g., data security, scalability, cost savings and Identification of workloads and applications that will be hosted alongside with assess to hardware & software requirements (servers,

storage, networking). The importance of ensuring compliance with regulatory and security policies will also be well defined.

2. **Infrastructure Setup:** Here, we look into Choosing between on-premises or third-party hosted private cloud, setting up physical hardware (servers, storage devices, networking), Implement virtualization using tools like VMware, Hyper-V, or KVM and establishing network configurations (firewalls, VLANs, load balancers).
3. **Cloud Management Software Installation.** Deploying cloud management software such as: OpenStack (open-source), VMware vSphere, Microsoft Azure Stack and OpenNebula are carried out in this stage. A general architecture of private cloud computing system is as shown below:

4. **Upcoming Challenges in the proposed smooth running of the cloud computing architecture**

Despite all the development and potential of cloud computing services, Hassan et al (2022) and Akand & Van Belle (2014) highlighted some possible challenges as follow:

1). **Security:** Cloud computing security is the main concern when making an investment in cloud computing services. The reason for this is that a third-party supplier stores and processes the users' data without their knowledge. The user becomes even more dubious when they learn about a certain organization's compromised credentials, account hacking, data breaches, and faulty authentication on a daily basis. Thankfully, cloud computing providers have started working to improve security features. Another way to exercise caution is to determine if the provider has access control protocols and a Secure User Identity Management System (SUIIMS) in place. Additionally, confirm that it adheres to privacy and database security guidelines.

2). **Password security:** One cloud account becomes more insecure as more people utilize it. Anyone who hacks into the cloud or knows a user's password will be able to view users' private information. The organization should use several levels of authentication in this situation and ensure that credentials are kept safe. Additionally, passwords should be changed frequently, particularly when a person leaves the company or resigns. Care should be taken while granting access to usernames and passwords.

3) **Cost management:** Cloud computing saves money on costly computer hardware, software, maintenance, and support while enabling users to access application software through a fast internet connection so as to reduce the price. However, it is challenging and expensive to modify the institution's requirements on the third-party platform. An additional cost, is

moving data to a public cloud, which is very costly for an organization.

4). **Internet connectivity:** Cloud services demand a high-speed internet connection. Therefore, in order to prevent downtime, relatively small institutions who are having connectivity issues should ideally first invest in a good internet connection. Because internet disruptions could entail large financial losses

5) **Lack of expertise:** The growing workload on cloud technologies and the ongoing development of cloud solutions have made its management more difficult. There has been a strong need for a workforce with the necessary training to handle cloud computing tools and services. To reduce this risk, the organization should and needs to train its IT staff.

6). **Compliance:** Another major risk associated with cloud computing is maintaining compliance. We describe compliance as a collection of guidelines that specify what information can be sent and what needs to be kept inside in order to maintain compliance. The compliance standards set forth by different government entities must be followed and respected by organizations.

7). **Creating a Private Cloud :** Implementing an internal cloud is desirable. This is due to the fact that all data are internally kept safe. The difficulty here is that the IT team has to start from scratch when building and fixing everything. The team also has to confirm that the cloud functions properly. They need to automate as many manual tasks as they can. It is important to finish tasks in the right order. Setting up a private cloud by one's effort seems difficult to accomplish.

8). **Performance:** The performance of a business depends on the provider when a client moves their institution's software to the cloud or a third-party vendor. Selecting the right cloud service provider is a major problem in cloud computing. We should look for providers with state-of-the-art technologies before making an investment. The supplier's systems are also linked to the functionality of

other cloud-based systems. When choosing a provider, exercise caution and make sure that they have procedures in place to handle issues that arise in real time.

9). **Portability and interoperability:** Programs must be able to be readily transferred between cloud providers without being locked in for an extended period of time, which is another problem with cloud computing. The flexibility of switching cloud providers is restricted due to the intricacy involved. A few additional problems are brought about by evolving cloud innovations, like tracking data flow and creating a secure network from the ground up. Another problem is that users cannot access it from anywhere. However, the cloud provider may fix, so that users can safely access the cloud from any location.

10). **High availability and reliability:** Sether (2016) stated that in cloud computing, reliability and high availability (HA) are two of the most pressing issues. While availability describes the likelihood that a system will be up and running at any given time, reliability is the potential that a system will be up and running at any given time. Since the majority of businesses depend on outside services, cloud solutions need to be reliable and strong. Cloud services are still not always available, which leads to frequent outages. Using in-house or external solutions to monitor the service is essential. It is essential to have plans for tracking SLAs, usage, performance, resilience, and business dependence on these services.

11). **Hybrid cloud complexity:** Helaimi (2023) stated that hybrid cloud environment is typically a jumbled mass of different cloud application development and cloud service providers, as well as private and public clouds, all functioning at the same time for any firm. These complicated cloud ecosystems lack a uniform user interface, consistent data, and analytical benefits for enterprises. In a hybrid cloud context, cloud computing is concerned

with scalability, integration, and disaster recovery amplified.

Conclusion

Recently, a new paradigm for hosting and providing services online has emerged: called cloud computing. Although it is still in its infancy and has numerous challenges that need to be resolved, it offers business owners several benefits. An application cloud configuration is essential to both service quality and business competitiveness. For the same performance goal, a flawed cloud architecture can cost up to twelve times as much. For recurrent operations that regularly execute comparable workloads, the savings from good cloud design are significantly higher.

However, choosing the best cloud setup is challenging due to the complexity of achieving high accuracy, minimal overhead, and adaptability for many applications at the same time. The supply of computing resources via the internet is known as cloud computing. Cost savings, scalability, high performance, economies of scale, and other benefits are all provided. A cloud migration is closely related to data and IT modernization for many businesses. Cloud computing architecture is composed of several components that work together to provide services to clients over the internet. These components include the Client Infrastructure, which offers a graphical user interface(GUI) for interacting with the cloud application, which can be any software or platform that a client wishes to use, the Service, which handles the type of service accessed based on the client's needs, the Runtime Cloud, which provides the execution and runtime environment for virtual machines, and Storage, which offers a massive quantity

of cloud storage space for storing and managing data.

Cloud computing has seen a significant increase in adoption in recent years, with major companies like Microsoft and Oracle encouraging users to upgrade to their cloud equivalents and a rise in cloud-native providers offering various services such as Software as a Service (SaaS), Platform as a Service (PaaS), and Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS). Additionally, edge computing has introduced the capability of evaluating data closer to the source before it is centralized in the cloud, which can significantly reduce data processing time and assist in turning data into insights through the application of AI and machine learning.

Akande et al (2013) stated that investing in cloud services comes with a variety of risks and challenges, including security concerns, cost management, internet connectivity, lack of expertise, compliance, control of governance, creating a private cloud, performance, interoperability and portability, high availability and reliability, and complexity in hybrid cloud environments. It is important for organizations to carefully consider these risks and challenges before making the decision to invest in cloud services, and to ensure that they have proper systems and processes in place to mitigate these risks and challenges. Akande et al (2013) stated that in addition, organizations should also consider the benefits of cloud services, such as cost savings, scalability, and flexibility, when making the decision to invest in cloud services. Delivering computing resources through the internet, such as storage, processing power, databases, networking, analytics, artificial intelligence, and software applications, is

known as cloud computing also called the cloud. Companies can get the computing resources they require whenever they need them by outsourcing these resources, eliminating the need to buy and maintain an on-site, physical IT infrastructure. This offers adaptable resources, quicker invention, and scale economies. A cloud migration is closely tied to data and IT transformation for many businesses

Even though cloud computing provides enormous prospects for the IT sector, cloud computing technology is still in its infancy, with numerous difficulties yet to be addressed especially in Delta State College Of Education, Mosogar, Delta State. We give a survey of cloud computing in this work, covering fundamental concepts, architectural principles, cutting-edge implementation, and research problems

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